

FORGING PATHS: TRAVERSING INTO THE LEADERSHIP QUALITIES OF THE SANGGUNIANG KABATAAN PRESIDENTS IN LA UNION, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

Politics is fundamental to societal development for young people as they play an important role in shaping political landscapes. This mixed methods study traversed into the leadership qualities and leadership skills of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) Federation Presidents in La Union, Philippines, and evaluated how these attributes affect their performance. A survey of 232 SK Chairpersons assessed eleven leadership qualities—vision, intelligence, charisma, responsibility/commitment, authenticity/integrity, drive/passion, courage, empathy, competence/experience, service orientation, and business orientation—and four leadership skills: idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration. All leadership qualities received top proficiency ratings, with vision, intelligence, responsibility/commitment, drive/passion, courage, empathy, competence/experience, and service orientation achieving exemplary levels, while charisma, authenticity/integrity, and business orientation got a slightly lower rating in some of their specific areas and the leadership skills uniformly rated as highly proficient. Semi structured interviews with 22 SK Chairpersons then explored how these attributes manifest in practice. Thematic analysis yielded five core themes: guiding the organization strategically, fostering connection and inclusivity, motivating and engaging the community, serving as role models to youth, and promoting innovation and problem-solving. Two subthemes also emerged: clear vision and direction, and shared vision. Slightly lower ratings in charisma, integrity/authenticity, and business orientation highlight areas for development. Based on these insights, the researchers propose a one-day leadership seminar focused on

charismatic communication, “walking the talk” to reinforce integrity, and innovative economic leadership for business orientation. This study contributes to the discourse on youth development by giving valuable insights into enhancing training programs and supporting future leaders in the Philippines.

Keywords: *Leadership qualities, leadership skills, mixed method, youth leadership, youth politics*

INTRODUCTION

Politics is an enduring feature of human society, emerging from the necessity to allocate limited resources, reconcile competing interests, and organize collective life (Rom et al., 2022). As Aristotle famously noted, “man is by nature a political animal,” emphasizing that political engagement is essential to human development and the flourishing of communities. Among the key actors in this arena are the youth—dynamic, idealistic, and increasingly recognized as catalysts for innovation and social change (Borojević et al., 2023).

The United Nations defines youth as individuals aged 15 to 24, representing a transitional stage marked by identity exploration and growing civic consciousness (Martin, 2022). Across different national contexts, youth participation has led to more responsive and sustainable governance outcomes. In India, youth-led co-creation enhances community accountability (Mathiyazhagan, 2020), while in Egypt, young people are instrumental in driving social transformation (Mansour, 2016). Globally, youth involvement in public affairs not only equips them for future leadership but also enriches policy-making with fresh perspectives (Macauley et al., 2022).

In the Philippines, youth participation is enshrined in Article II, Section 13 of the 1987 Constitution, which acknowledges the youth’s vital role in nation-building. To institutionalize this participation, Republic Act No. 7160—the Local Government Code of 1991—established the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK), a grassroots youth council that empowers young Filipinos to engage in governance at the barangay level (Balod & Goño, 2010). Subsequent reforms, including Republic Act No. 10742 (2015), have further enhanced the structure and responsibilities of SK officials to ensure meaningful youth leadership at the municipal and provincial levels (Navarro et al., 2023).

While numerous studies have examined the general structure and challenges of the SK system, there is limited research focusing on the leadership attributes of SK Federation Presidents—particularly in La Union. These young leaders play a crucial role in shaping policy, mobilizing their peers, and representing the youth sector in local governance. However, their effectiveness depends on both innate qualities and learned leadership skills.

This study addresses this gap by examining: (1) the leadership qualities—such as vision, intelligence, charisma, responsibility/commitment, authenticity/integrity, drive/passion, courage, empathy, competence/experience, service orientation, and business orientation; (2) the leadership skills—including idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration—demonstrated by SK Federation Presidents in La Union; and (3) the impact of these attributes on their performance. Grounded in Trait Theory, Transformational Leadership Theory, and Situational Leadership Theory, the research employs a mixed-methods approach. Ultimately, the findings aim to inform a proposed leadership seminar tailored to strengthen youth governance capacities and support the SK as a foundation for the country's next generation of leaders.

Research Questions

The study aimed to examine the leadership qualities and skills of Sangguniang Kabataan Federation presidents in La Union. Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What are the leadership qualities of Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in La Union along:
 - a. Vision;
 - b. Intelligence;
 - c. Charisma;
 - d. Responsibility/ Commitment;
 - e. Authenticity/ Integrity;
 - f. Drive/ Passion;
 - g. Courage;
 - h. Empathy;
 - i. Competence/ Experience;
 - j. Service Orientation; and
 - k. Business Orientation?
2. What are the leadership skills of Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in La Union along:
 - a. Idealized Influence;
 - b. Inspirational Motivation;
 - c. Intellectual Stimulation; and
 - d. Individualize Consideration?
3. How do these leadership attributes affect the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in La Union?
4. What proposed leadership training seminar can be made to understand the leadership qualities and skills of Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in La Union?

METHODOLOGY

An explanatory sequential mixed methods design was employed (Leavy, 2017). Quantitative data were collected and analyzed first to determine prevailing leadership qualities and skills among Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) Federation Presidents. These findings then informed a qualitative phase, in which semi structured interviews were conducted to explore how these attributes influenced leadership performance. This design was supported by a descriptive research framework to examine patterns and traits within their governance roles (Rahi, 2017).

For the quantitative phase, 232 SK Chairpersons from La Union's City of San Fernando and 19 municipalities participated. A stratified random sampling technique ensured proportional representation across all local government units (LGUs). The sample size was determined using Raosoft Calculator (95% confidence level; 0.5 margin of error), ensuring high internal and external validity (Thomas, 2023).

For the qualitative phase, 22 SK Chairpersons were purposively selected based on (1) willingness to participate and (2) at least three years of public service. Data collection continued until saturation was reached—at 10 participants—consistent with Creswell's (2014) guideline that saturation occurs when no new themes emerge.

The survey questionnaire, adapted from Qunitip (2021) and Bass's Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (1985), assessed leadership qualities (Research Question 1) and leadership skills (Research Question 2) using 4-point Likert scales for agreement and frequency. The tool was validated by four experts—a quantitative research specialist, a former SK Federation President, a DILG officer, and a LYDC officer—and was pilot-tested with 31 SK Chairpersons from Tagudin, Ilocos Sur, resulting in a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.90, indicating excellent internal consistency.

A semi-structured interview guide was also developed to explore how leadership attributes affect performance (Research Question 3). It was validated by three experts: a qualitative research specialist, a former SK Federation President, and a Local Youth Development Council officer.

Quantitative data were processed using Microsoft Excel, with the mode used to determine central tendencies across leadership indicators. Leadership qualities were measured through a 4-point Likert agreement scale, where 4 indicated Strongly Agree (Exemplary Leadership), 3 = Agree (Strong Leadership), 2 = Disagree (Moderate Leadership), and 1 = Strongly Disagree (Limited Leadership). Leadership skills were evaluated using a 4-point Likert frequency scale: 4 signified Strongly Agree (Highly Proficient), 3 = Agree (Proficient), 2 = Disagree (Moderately Proficient), and 1 = Strongly Disagree (Minimally Proficient).

For the qualitative phase, Thematic Analysis was employed following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase process: familiarization with data through intelligent transcription, coding of initial concepts, theme generation, theme review, theme naming,

and final write-up. To ensure credibility and validity, participant responses were verified through transcript triangulation, with each respondent reviewing and signing a Certificate of Transcription Accuracy.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Leadership qualities of Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in La Union

Leadership Qualities

Table 1 summarizes the modal scores for the eleven leadership qualities assessed among Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) Federation Presidents in La Union. The majority of indicators—including vision, intelligence, responsibility/commitment, drive/passion, courage, empathy, competence/experience, and service orientation—achieved the highest possible mode of 4 (Strongly Agree – Exemplary Leadership), suggesting that these qualities are core strengths consistently demonstrated by the respondents. In contrast, charisma, authenticity/integrity, and business orientation yielded a slightly lower mode of 3 (Agree – Strong Leadership), indicating generally strong performance but with potential for enhancement in terms of inspirational influence, ethical transparency, and strategic innovation.

Vision

Visionary leadership was consistently rated exemplary (mode = 4). SK Presidents demonstrated strong strategic foresight, the ability to anticipate change, and a clear articulation of long-term goals. This aligns with Khan et al. (2017) and Strange and Mumford (2002), who assert that vision allows leaders to unify teams and pursue meaningful change. These findings affirm the SK Presidents' capacity to navigate complex environments and ensure sustained organizational relevance.

Table 1. Leadership Qualities of the Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents In La Union

Quality	Mode	Descriptive Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Vision	4	SA	EL

Intelligence	4	SA	EL
Charisma	3	A	SL
Responsibility/ Commitment	4	SA	EL
Authenticity/ Integrity	3	A	SL
Drive/Passion	4	SA	EL
Courage	4	SA	EL
Empathy	4	SA	EL
Competence/ Experience	4	SA	EL
Service Orientation	4	SA	EL
Business Orientation	3	A	SL

Legend: 4 Strongly Agree (SA) Exemplary Leadership (EL)
3 Agree (A) Strong Leadership (SL)

Intelligence

SK Presidents received the highest rating (mode = 4) for intelligence. Their ability to analyze information, solve problems, and make sound decisions reflects high cognitive and strategic capacity. This supports Barret et al.'s (2024) triarchic theory of intelligence, suggesting that a blend of analytical, creative, and practical intelligence underpins effective leadership in local governance.

Charisma

Charisma received a mode of 3 (Strong Leadership), showing solid performance in interpersonal skills and motivational presence. However, opportunities remain to amplify influence and inspire followers toward ambitious goals. The findings echo Vergauwe et al. (2018) and Pan et al. (2019), who note that charismatic leaders must pair emotional appeal with strategic direction for maximum impact.

Responsibility/Commitment

Rated as exemplary (mode = 4), responsibility and commitment were evident in the SK Presidents' alignment with organizational goals, persistence, and promotion of public accountability. Their reliability and consistency resonate with Quandt (2023) and Ribeiro et al. (2018), who link organizational success with leader dedication and integrity.

Authenticity/Integrity

With a mode of 3, authenticity/integrity was perceived as a strength with room for enhancement. While SK Presidents were viewed as ethical and trustworthy, some inconsistencies were noted. The findings align with Avolio et al. (2011) and Covelli and Mason (2017), who stress that maintaining credibility requires unwavering transparency and value alignment across situations.

Drive/Passion

Drive or passion achieved a mode of 4, confirming that SK Presidents are deeply committed to youth development and resilient in facing setbacks. As Gallos and Bolman (2021) suggest, emotionally invested leadership energizes teams and drives results. The findings affirm the SK leaders' sincerity and enthusiasm in achieving impact.

Courage

Courage also scored the highest rating (mode = 4), reflecting a willingness to make bold, ethical decisions in the face of adversity. This aligns with Kidder and Bracy (2001) and Bennis and Thomas (2002), who emphasize that courageous leadership builds trust and positions leaders to manage transformative change.

Empathy

Rated exemplary (mode = 4), empathy emerged as a cornerstone of SK leadership. Presidents demonstrated strong sensitivity to constituents' needs and diverse perspectives, aligning with Edmondson and Lei (2014) and Seijts and Milani (2021), who link empathetic leadership to inclusivity, collaboration, and organizational cohesion.

Competence/Experience

Competence and experience received a mode of 4. SK Presidents were recognized for their legal knowledge, coalition-building, and strategic thinking—qualities supported by Serrat (2019) and Vaculik et al. (2014), who view accumulated experience as central to leadership maturity and impact.

Service Orientation

Service orientation was consistently rated exemplary (mode = 4), showing the SK Presidents' prioritization of public welfare over personal interest. Their alignment with

servant leadership principles (Botelho, 2021; Hogan et al., 1984) reflects a commitment to inclusivity, empowerment, and sustainable development.

Business Orientation

Business orientation received an overall mode of 3, with one indicator scoring 4. This suggests foundational capability in innovation and strategy, but a need for growth in foresight and economic collaboration. Schwarz and Wach (2024), and Pandey (2023) emphasize that economic insight and adaptability are essential to sustainable local governance.

Leadership skills of Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in La Union

Table 2 presents the modal scores for the four transformational leadership skills assessed among Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) Federation Presidents in La Union. All four indicators—idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration—achieved the highest possible mode of 4 (Strongly Agree – Highly Proficient). These results highlight a consistently strong proficiency in transformational leadership behaviors, suggesting that SK Federation Presidents are effective in inspiring peers, stimulating innovative thinking, and responding to individual needs within their leadership roles.

Table 2. Leadership Skills of the Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in La Union

Skill	Mode	Descriptive Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Idealized Influence	4	SA	HP
Inspirational Motivation	4	SA	HP
Intellectual Stimulation	4	SA	HP

Legend: 4 Strongly Agree (SA) Highly Proficient (HP)

Idealized Influence

SK Federation Presidents consistently demonstrated integrity, transparency, and a commitment to ethical conduct (mode = 4). By serving as role models and upholding inclusive practices, they fostered community trust and engagement. This is consistent with Afshari (2021) and Okoli et al. (2021) who emphasize that leaders who exemplify values inspire collective resilience and collaborative spirit.

Inspirational Motivation

Rated highly proficient (mode = 4), SK Presidents excelled in communicating vision, modeling resilience, and empowering innovation. Their capacity to motivate followers aligns with Towler (2020) and Hasija et al. (2019), who highlight that transformational leaders inspire by cultivating purpose, support systems, and shared optimism.

Intellectual Stimulation

All indicators under this dimension scored 4, indicating a high level of engagement with continuous learning and strategic thinking. SK Presidents promoted creative problemsolving, professional development, and collaboration with peers—behaviors validated by Boyd & Hartzell (2023) and the American Psychological Association (2022).

Individualized Consideration

Individualized consideration was rated highly proficient (mode = 4), showcasing the SK Presidents' ability to provide tailored support and mentorship. Their actions reflect transformational leadership practices as described by Towler (2020) and Boyd and Hartzell (2023) where leaders engage followers personally to foster belonging, growth, and collaboration.

The Effect of Leadership Qualities on the Performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in La Union

Key-informant interviews (n = 22) generated two major thematic categories corresponding to (a) leadership qualities and (b) leadership skills. Within each, subthemes illustrate how attributes manifest in the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in La Union.

Theme 1. Guiding the Organization Strategically

SK Federation Presidents demonstrated the ability to strategically guide their organizations through visionary planning, collaborative goal-setting, and responsive leadership. Informants consistently emphasized the Presidents' role in shaping organizational direction and aligning stakeholders around common priorities.

Clear Vision and Direction. SK Federation Presidents articulated clear and compelling visions that served as strategic frameworks for youth programs and community initiatives. Informants such as K11 (*“he shared his vision even before running as SK Chairman”*), K14 (*“she has a vision that the Bagulin youth will break barriers and showcase their talents”*), K118 (*“a clear vision acts as a roadmap”*), K119 (*“she stays focused on her goals and leads by example”*), and K122 (*“he ensures projects are done*

properly and on time") highlighted how these visions motivated collective action and accountability.

The strategic leadership approach aligns with Child's (1972) concept of "strategic choice," where influential leaders shape organizational direction based on context and opportunity. Strategic thinkers integrate vision with operational clarity, enabling teams to develop meaningful goals responsive to grassroots needs (Whitlock, 2004). The Presidents' ability to navigate change with confidence also supports Bridges' (1991) framework on leadership transitions, wherein leaders contextualize uncertainty as opportunity. Their consistency in vision-setting reflects Kouzes and Posner's (2021) emphasis on leadership credibility through forward-looking commitment. As Mafriqi (2023) notes, a vision that connects individual aspirations to broader organizational outcomes fosters engagement and purpose, particularly among youth. This clarity is vital in SK governance, where direction shapes policy, outreach, and impact.

Shared Vision. In addition to articulating individual goals, SK Presidents cultivated a sense of shared purpose across teams and communities. KI13 (*"he inspires and motivates the youth, effectively manages projects, and fosters collaboration"*), KI16 (*"her vision aligns with ours—we're all moving in the same direction"*), KI20 (*"her clean environment vision motivated youth to participate"*), KI21 (*"he articulates a vision that guides decisions and actions"*), and KI22 (*"his clarity ensures everyone aligns with common goals"*) described how collective ownership of vision led to trust, cohesion, and sustained community effort.

This shared vision resonates with Senge's (1990) view of vision as a "common mental model" that guides coordinated action. It aligns with Zasa et al. (2022), who underscore shared vision's role in managing decentralized youth organizations through unified yet flexible leadership. Additionally, the motivation instilled by shared purpose reflects the findings of Dare (2022) and the University of Sussex (2024), both of which link vision with team alignment, morale, and community ownership. Leadership theorists such as Košičiarová et al. (2021) and Wang et al. (2009) emphasize that effective leaders motivate teams not by top-down direction but by modeling and fostering commitment to shared objectives. The data from La Union illustrates this principle in practice. By embracing and communicating a collective goal, SK Presidents function as transformational leaders—enabling collaboration, promoting trust, and achieving tangible results.

Theme 2: Fostering Connection and Inclusivity

The ability to build inclusive relationships emerged as a defining leadership trait. KI4, KI7, KI20, and KI22 described SK Presidents who listened empathetically, adapted programs to youth needs, and prioritized the collective good. For example, KI22 praised a President who *"creates initiatives that respond to the needs of the community,"* while KI20 highlighted her effort to *"listen to our ideas and ensure everyone felt included."* KI7 and KI4 also recounted how the Presidents supported team members during personal struggles, showing concern that extended beyond formal roles. These actions mirror the

inclusive leadership framework of Ely et al. (2002) and Randel et al. (2018), where equity, trust, and shared decision-making are central to meaningful engagement.

Such leadership not only enhances organizational unity but also amplifies innovation and trust across diverse stakeholders (Korkmaz et al., 2022). The Presidents' responsiveness and sensitivity underscore the role of emotional intelligence in youth leadership. As Sharma (2024) suggests, when leaders prioritize inclusive engagement, they elevate community capacity and credibility. The SK Presidents' approach aligns with transformational leadership values—particularly servant leadership—where leaders act not as authorities but as facilitators of belonging, support, and growth (Dare, 2022).

Theme 3: Motivating and Engaging the Community

SK Federation Presidents also excelled at inspiring participation and building a sense of collective purpose. Informants including K11 (*“he gathered all schools for a federationwide competition—first time it happened”*), K14 (*“she motivates the youth to actively join programs”*), and K18 (*“she has charisma and always captures attention during sessions”*) highlighted how Presidents galvanized action. K110 and K122 described how Presidents promoted collaboration: *“he engages the team and creates a collaborative atmosphere”* and *“he builds trust and enthusiasm because he is approachable.”* Meanwhile, K115 noted how motivation extended beyond events to personal development: *“he inspired youth to pursue not just medals but their dreams.”*

This motivation stems from a foundation of trust, as described by Westover (2023). Leaders who foster open communication and reliability earn support and encourage civic engagement. Stuart (2022) adds that effective leaders socialize their communities to solve shared problems—echoed in the Presidents' use of participatory initiatives. The Presidents' behavior aligns with Cherry's (2024) transformational leadership theory, where enthusiasm, trust, and empowerment foster long-term engagement. By fostering a culture of encouragement and action, SK Presidents turn programs into platforms for youth development and community unity.

Fig. 1. Thematic Map of the Effect of Leadership Qualities on the Performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in La Union

The Effect of Leadership Skills on the Performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in La Union

Theme 1: Role Model to the Youth

SK Federation Presidents served as exemplary figures within their organizations and communities. Informants such as K18 (*“she led by example, displaying integrity and responsibility”*), K116 (*“she’s a role model who motivates and unites us despite disagreements”*), K118 (*“she walks the talk”*), K119 (*“she earned trust by being a role model to fellow SK Chairpersons”*), K120 (*“her idealized influence makes us want to follow her lead”*), and K122 (*“you can see his ethics and values, which inspire us to follow”*) emphasized how these leaders' consistent actions reinforced credibility and motivated emulation. Their leadership practices cultivated trust and set standards for ethical behavior and professional responsibility. This aligns with Bandura's (1986) observational learning theory, which posits that youth learn behaviors by observing those they respect. Smetana et al. (2014) and Atif et al. (2022) also affirm that role models promote character development, self-esteem, and resilience. The SK Federation Presidents' mentorship, visibility, and integrity clearly fostered admiration, shaping how young people understood and practiced leadership.

Theme 2: Promoting Innovation and Problem-Solving

The SK Federation Presidents demonstrated proactive and adaptive leadership by promoting creativity, encouraging alternative perspectives, and initiating solutions to community issues. Informants such as K122 (*“he encouraged us to think outside the box and explore sustainability ideas”*), K11 (*“he organized seminars and introduced a budgeting app to solve common problems”*), K16 (*“he helps us draft everything we need”*), K18 (*“he engaged everyone in creative problem-solving”*), and K110 (*“his legal studies guide his leadership and compliance with governance standards”*) described instances where innovation and strategic thinking were key to overcoming challenges. These findings support Shafique et al. (2019), who underscore that transformational and ethical leaders inspire creativity through support and high moral standards. The Presidents' emphasis on knowledge-sharing, continuous learning, and community-based innovation affirmed their ability to nurture environments where collaboration and creative problem-solving thrive.

Fig. 2. Thematic Map of Effect of Leadership Skills on the Performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in La Union

Proposed Leadership Training Seminar

Based on the study's findings, the SK Federation Presidents in La Union exhibit exemplary leadership qualities and highly proficient leadership skills, as evidenced by

favorable evaluations from their respective SK Chairpersons. However, indicators such as charisma, authenticity/integrity, and business orientation scored slightly lower compared to other traits, signaling areas for targeted development.

To address these gaps, a one-day leadership training seminar titled "Leadership Unleashed: Leadership Qualities AND Skills Development Workshops for Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) Federation Presidents" is proposed. This program aims to refine these identified areas by enhancing interpersonal engagement, reinforcing ethical leadership, and boosting business and economic foresight. Through lectures, interactive activities, and collaborative workshops, SK Federation Presidents will gain the tools needed to elevate their performance and impact.

This training seminar, organized by the College of Arts and Sciences BA Political Science in coordination with the MLUC Extension Unit and PPSK Officers, is scheduled for March 20, 2025. Participants include SK Federation Presidents across La Union, with funding support from the Panlalawigan Pederasyon ng Sangguniang Kabataan ng La Union. By empowering these youth leaders through targeted leadership development, the program seeks to promote transformational governance and ensure a more capable, inclusive, and visionary leadership core within the SK Federation. The seminar stands as a concrete response to the study's recommendations and a strategic investment in the future of local governance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were made:

1. The Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) Federation Presidents in La Union consistently demonstrate exemplary leadership qualities, excelling particularly in vision, intelligence, responsibility, passion, empathy, and service orientation. Their capacity to foster trust, inclusivity, and innovation contributes to sustainable development and community empowerment. However, areas such as charisma, authenticity/integrity, and business orientation present opportunities for further development. Overall, their transformative leadership positions them as catalysts for meaningful progress and youth empowerment.
2. The leadership skills of the Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in La Union demonstrated exceptional effectiveness in fostering ethical, empathetic, and strategic governance. By embodying through their mastery of idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration, they created a culture of trust, empowerment, and continuous growth. As a result, their leadership skills were highly effective in fostering a sense of unity, responsibility, and empowerment within the community, contributing to the success of their governance.
3. The leadership qualities and skills of the Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in La Union have significantly contributed to their performance and the success of their governance. Their leadership attributes enabled them to foster

innovation, inspire community involvement, and address diverse needs, as well as cultivate an environment of trust, empowerment, and continuous growth that drives into meaningful progress and positive outcomes for their communities. Thus, these leadership attributes of the Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents strengthen the development and resilience of the communities that they serve.

4. A leadership training seminar focused on enhancing leadership qualities could significantly improve the performance of Sangguniang Kabataan Federation Presidents in areas where they received lower ratings, specifically in charisma, authenticity/integrity, and business orientation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby suggested:

1. To enhance charisma and authenticity/integrity, SK Federation Presidents should be encouraged to participate in youth leadership debate forums and public-speaking engagements. These platforms can improve their confidence, communication skills, and ability to engage diverse perspectives—key components of charismatic and authentic leadership. To strengthen business orientation, they should build partnerships with local government units, private sectors, and NGOs. Training in networking and collaborative leadership will enable them to mobilize resources and implement scalable, community responsive initiatives.
2. Further studies on the leadership skills of the SK Federation Presidents focus on the four components of Transformational Leadership, which are idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration. Their idealized influence would help the SK Federation Presidents develop ethical leadership and build trust, acting as a role model for others. In Inspirational motivation studies would teach the SK Federation Presidents how to effectively communicate a compelling vision, energize the youth, and foster a shared sense of purpose. Enhancing intellectual stimulation would also equip the President with strategies to promote critical thinking, creativity, and innovative problem-solving among youth leaders. And for individualized consideration would help the SK Federation Presidents learn to offer personalized mentorship, understand the unique needs of team members, and provide tailored support for their growth.
3. Future research should examine how SK Federation Presidents demonstrate their transformational leadership in practice—particularly in communication, decision-making, emotional intelligence, and conflict resolution. Understanding these skills will provide deeper insights into how they build collaboration, trust, and effective governance within their federations and communities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical clearance was secured from the DMMMSU Research Ethics Committee prior to data collection. Quantitative data were collected through both paper-based and Google Forms surveys during the first semester through the mid-second semester. Qualitative interviews were conducted either on-site, typically in barangay halls, or online via Google Meet, depending on the participants' preferences. Informed consent was obtained in writing, and all interviews were recorded (with permission), then transcribed, translated, and anonymized using pseudonyms. Follow-up questions were asked as necessary to clarify responses.

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